

THE IMPORTANCE OF FAMILY AND SCHOOL PARTNERSHIP IN THE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS WITH MENTAL DISABILITY

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Annotation: *This article highlights the importance of family-school partnerships in the education of students with intellectual disabilities and some modern interactive methods.*

Key words: *mental retarded child, parents, partnership, interactive, pedagog.*

Every child must be educated in school today. There are enough conditions for this. In particular, there are enough auxiliary schools and inclusive classes. But there is only one requirement, school and family should cooperate in order to provide high-quality and effective education for mentally retarded students. In order to get to know the parents of mentally retarded students well, work with parents will be planned in advance. Therefore, we start our work by analyzing the social composition of parents, their mood and the child's stay in our special school. We will conduct surveys and personal interviews on this topic, which will help to properly organize the work, make it effective, and choose interesting forms of interaction with families with mentally retarded children.[1]

In addition to traditional forms of work of specialized school educational organization and family, innovative forms and methods of work are actively used:

- "round discussion" on any topic;
- thematic exhibitions;
- social expertise, diagnostics, tests, inquiry on any topic;
- expert advice;
- family sports meetings;
- open classes for parents;
- competition of family talents;
- portfolio of family success;
- Open day;
- the site of the specialized assistant school.[2]

The advantages of the new system of interaction between the specialized special school and the family are indisputable:

- This is a positive emotional attitude of teachers and parents to work together in raising mentally retarded students.
- This is information about the individuality of a student with mental retardation.
- parents can independently choose and form this direction of development and upbringing of a school-aged child;
- This is to strengthen relationships within the family,
- This specialized special school is an opportunity to implement a unique program on education and family upbringing and development of a child.
- This is an opportunity to take into account the type of family and the style of family relations.

The teacher can determine the type of family of the student, find the right approach for interaction and work successfully with parents.

When implementing a new system of interaction with the family, it is important to avoid the shortcomings inherent in the old forms of working with the family.

Children of active parents increase their self-confidence, ask more questions about family and school, and students take initiative when they see the interest and activity of parents. The close communication between the teacher and his parents, emotional upliftment, the student who sees the participation of parents in all organizational activities, has a close and warm relationship with the teacher and his parents and feels like a member of the society. feels the need for And as a result, a new positive attitude of parents towards the specialized special school, a positive assessment of its activities was given. Thus, the use of various forms of work with families of students of specialized auxiliary schools gives positive results. In all their work, specialized assistant school employees prove to parents that their involvement in pedagogical activities, their interest in the educational process is important, not because the pedagogue (teacher) wants it, but because it is necessary for the development of their child.[3]

In order to solve the tasks set in the educational organization of the specialized special school, work is planned in three directions:

1. Organization of interaction with the family with the employees of the specialized special preschool organization, introducing teachers to the system of new forms of working with parents.
2. Improving the pedagogical culture of parents.
3. Involvement of parents in the activities of the specialized auxiliary school team, joint work on sharing experience.

A specialized auxiliary school is in development mode, considered a mobile system, and responds quickly to changes in the social structure of parents, their educational needs and educational requirements. Accordingly, the forms and directions of the specialized preschool education organization's work with the family should change.[4]

It was noted that one of the principles of the specialized special school is to organize work with the family, which is the basis of helping parents in raising mentally retarded children, protecting and strengthening their physical and mental health. development of individual abilities and necessary correction of disorders in their development. One of the requirements for psychological-pedagogical conditions is the requirement for psychological-pedagogical support and professional development of the family.

Paying attention to the purpose of cooperation with the family, if the upbringing and education of a mentally retarded child is corrected, a person who can contribute to society, can satisfy his own needs, and has a certain place in society. matures. The above is clearly visible when it comes to the role of the special school and the family in the education of mentally retarded students and is the basis of this current topic.[5] It is known that the environment is one of the main tools for the development of a child's personality, the source of his social experience and knowledge, and it not only provides a variety of activities for a preschool child, but is also a form of self-education. It also forms the basis of independent activity. The environment is the social, social, material and spiritual conditions that surround the child's existences.

REFERENCES:

1. Кан-Калик В. А. Педагогическая деятельность как творческий процесс. — М.: Педагогика, 2007. — 144 с
2. Андреева Г. М. Социальная психология. М.: Аспект Пресс. 2000
3. Гайдукевич С.Е., Гайслер В., Готан Ф. и др. Обучение и воспитание детей в условиях центра коррекционно-развивающего обучения и реабилитации. Пособие для педагогов и родителей. 2008.
4. Загорская, Е.А. Тренинг общения для родителей, имеющих детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья Текст. / Е.А. Загорская // Воспитание и обучение детей с нарушениями развития. 2004. - № 5. - С. 67-70.
5. Дементьева, Н.Ф., Багаева, Г.Н., Исаева, Т.Н. Социальная работа с семьей ребенка с ограниченными возможностями. М., 2006